

CITRIC ACID PRODUCTION FROM PINEAPPLE WASTE

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ABSTRACT

Aspergillus niger and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* were grown on pineapple waste and their citric acid production characteristics compared. The effects of pH and methanol on the production were investigated. The highest concentration of citric acid was produced by *A. niger* at initial pH of 4.5 in the presence of methanol. Addition of methanol stimulated the biomass production, carbon IV oxide concentration and sugar utilization.

KEYWORDS: Citric acid, methanol, *Aspergillus niger*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*

INTRODUCTION

Because of the current interest in the economic conversion of renewable resources to value added products like alcohols and organic acid, residue of a number of plant crops have been evaluated as substrates (Ban-Koffi and Han, 1992; Alben *et al.*, 2003; Alben and Erkmen, 2004; Prado *et al.*, 2005; Xie and West, 2006). Materials like molasses corncobs, apple and grape pomace, orange and brewery waste have been used as substrate in citric acid production. Citric acid (2-hydroxy-1, 2, 3- propanetricarboxylic acid) is produced by either submerged or surface fermentation (Alben and Erkmen, 2004) employing various carbohydrate sources (Pandey *et al.*, 2000). *Aspergillus niger* is the most widely used microorganism for citric acid production. Citric acid is a popular component made use of in the food and pharmaceutical industry synthesized by the fungus *A. niger* in an industrial scale submerged fermentation process. Citric acid exists in a variety of fruits and vegetables notably citrus fruits. Lemons and limes have been reported to have high concentration of this acid (Penniston *et al.*, 2008).

Pineapple waste, consisting mainly of cellulose and starch was suggested as a valuable fermentation and non fermentation products (Tewari *et al.*, 1987) Pineapple waste from canneries has been utilized as the substrate for bromelin, vinegar, wine, food/feed yeast and alcohol (Dev and Ingle, 1982; Ban-Koffi and Han, 1992). There is a dearth of information on the use of pineapple for citric acid production. Reduction in the cost of production can be achieved by using less expensive substrates like pineapple waste. This paper evaluates the potential of pineapple waste as substrate for citric acid production by *Aspergillus niger* and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Microorganisms: *Aspergillus niger* and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* were used in this study. They were cultured on Potato Dextrose agar (PDA) at 30°C for 5days. *A. niger* spores were produced in 250 mL Erlenmeyer flasks containing 40 mL PDA medium. The medium was inoculated with spores from the stock cultures and incubated at 28 °C for seven days. The spores were recovered by stirring using a solution of Tween 80 (0.01 %). The suspension obtained containing 10⁸ spores/ mL was stored at 4 °C for up to seven days.

Fermentation media: Experiments were performed in 250 mL Erlenmeyer flasks containing 200 mL of fermentation media which were prepared at pH = 4.5, 5.5 and 6.5 in the presence of 0.01 % (w/v) or 0.02g of pineapple waste. The pineapple waste comprises of the whole component of the pineapple fruit (skin, crown and pulp) being grounded properly and mixed together. One percent volume fraction (0.2 mL) of methanol was added to half portion of the flasks containing the fermentation media. The pH of the medium was adjusted using either 0.2M NaOH or H₂SO₄. The media were sterilized at 121°C for 15 min. Each flask was inoculated with 0.1 % of spore suspension. Inoculated flasks were wrist shaken at 30°C for 14 days.

Table 1: Changes in biomass production (%) throughout the fermentation period.

Samples	Biomass (%)							
	pH	Day2	Day4	Day6	Day8	Day10	Day12	Day14
<i>A.niger</i>								
Pineapple waste	4.5	5.0	8.0	13.0	18.0	18.0	20.0	21.0
	5.5	0.0	0.0	6.0	11.0	13.0	15.0	17.0
	6.5	0.0	3.0	3.0	6.0	14.0	14.0	16.0
Pineapple waste+1% methanol	4.5	8.0	12.0	14.0	14.0	17.0	18.0	19.0
	5.5	8.0	10.0	15.0	15.0	15.0	16.0	18.0
	6.5	7.0	10.0	14.0	14.0	14.0	17.0	19.0
<i>S. cerevisiae</i>								
Pineapple waste	4.5	4.0	6.0	13.0	14.0	14.0	15.0	15.0
	5.5	11.0	16.0	17.0	17.0	19.0	19.0	19.0
	6.5	7.0	9.0	12.0	14.0	18.0	18.0	19.0
Pineapple waste+1% methanol	4.5	2.0	8.0	13.0	13.0	18.0	18.0	20.0
	5.5	6.0	9.0	10.0	16.0	17.0	17.0	18.0
	6.5	3.0	5.0	13.0	15.0	16.0	17.0	18.0

Table 2: Changes in the citric acid concentration (%m/v) throughout the fermentation period.

Samples	Citric acid (%m/v)							
	pH	Day2	Day4	Day6	Day8	Day10	Day12	Day14
<i>A.niger</i>								
Pineapple waste	4.5	0.032	0.041	0.061	0.086	0.102	0.116	0.118
	5.5	0.033	0.039	0.056	0.087	0.092	0.104	0.106
	6.5	0.031	0.039	0.046	0.054	0.056	0.068	0.070
Pineapple waste+1% methanol	4.5	0.067	0.082	0.105	0.113	0.128	0.145	0.147
	5.5	0.049	0.066	0.082	0.098	0.114	0.128	0.130
	6.5	0.025	0.034	0.051	0.067	0.082	0.096	0.098
<i>S. cerevisiae</i>								
Pineapple waste	4.5	0.024	0.027	0.035	0.048	0.057	0.064	0.066
	5.5	0.016	0.024	0.031	0.032	0.051	0.059	0.061
	6.5	0.008	0.020	0.033	0.040	0.049	0.056	0.056
Pineapple waste+1% methanol	4.5	0.051	0.064	0.081	0.097	0.114	0.129	0.131
	5.5	0.034	0.050	0.065	0.082	0.100	0.113	0.115
	6.5	0.016	0.035	0.048	0.067	0.086	0.102	0.104

NB: Initial citric acid (%m/v) in fresh sample = 0.016%

The content of the fermentation flasks were analyzed for citric acid, sugar, CO₂ and biomass content at every two-day interval. The pH was also monitored.

ANALYTICAL METHODS

Determination of biomass content: The suspension was filtered through Whatman No 1 filter paper to remove mycelium. The filter cake on paper was washed thrice with deionised water, dried at 105 °C to a constant mass in an oven (Gallenkamp) and weighed as the biomass.

Determination of citric acid content: The titrimetric method was employed (Chemlab.truman.edu, 2006). The amount of citric acid in the filtrate was measured by titration with 0.1M NaOH against phenolphthalein as an indicator. The concentration of citric acid was calculated from the total acidity minus that of the blank assuming that the acid was only composed of citric acid.

Table 3: Changes in CO₂ production (mg/L) throughout the fermentation period.

Samples	CO ₂ (mg/L)							
	pH	Day2	Day4	Day6	Day8	Day10	Day12	Day14
<i>A.niger</i>								
Pineapple waste	4.5	94.15	120.85	129.4	175.79	199.76	219.74	239.71
	5.5	68.11	89.89	89.89	169.80	190.77	199.76	211.75
	6.5	24.40	49.94	64.92	80.90	141.83	163.80	182.78
Pineapple waste+1% methanol	4.5	31.28	54.93	59.93	140.83	276.67	301.64	356.57
	5.5	25.67	44.95	60.93	199.76	234.72	271.67	308.63
	6.5	20.04	34.96	44.95	90.89	187.77	224.73	288.65
<i>S. cerevisiae</i>								
Pineapple waste	4.5	58.14	79.90	89.89	127.84	149.82	159.80	169.80
	5.5	43.01	44.94	62.92	104.87	179.78	199.76	219.73
	6.5	30.19	34.96	56.93	99.88	194.76	209.75	229.73
Pineapple waste+1% methanol	4.5	30.15	34.96	39.95	179.78	219.74	233.72	250.70
	5.5	20.19	21.97	34.96	119.86	176.78	204.75	228.83
	6.5	19.87	24.97	34.96	119.76	229.72	240.71	253.70

Table 4: Glucose consumption (%) in pineapple waste by test organisms

Initial pH	Pineapple waste		Pineapple waste +1% methanol	
	Glucose (%)		Glucose (%)	
	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>
4.5	5.76	6.84	5.64	6.96
5.5	5.88	6.72	5.88	7.68
6.5	5.52	6.36	5.28	7.08

Initial glucose (%) in fresh sample = 8.16%

Determination of CO₂ content: The titrimetric method described by Caputi *et al.* (1970) was used. Titration was carried out with 0.02M NaOH.

Determination of total carbohydrate: Total CHO of the filtrate at various times was determined as glucose by anthrone sulphuric acid method (Alben *et al.*, 2004). The pH was determined with a digital pH meter.

RESULTS

A rapid increase in biomass production was observed until the tenth day and became almost constant till the end of the fermentation period (Table 1). The sample inoculated with *A.niger* without *methanol* at initial pH of 4.5 produced the highest concentration of biomass (21 %). A rapid increase occurred in all samples between the sixth and eight and gradually decreased till the end of the fermentation. Citric acid production increased rapidly from the onset of the fermentation but became almost constant towards the end of the fermentation (Table 2). The highest citric acid level on the pineapple waste was produced by *A. niger*. The presence of *methanol* facilitated an increase in citric acid production. The highest amount of citric acid (0.147% mass/volume) was produced by *A. niger* in the presence of *methanol* at an initial pH of 4.5 (Table 2).

Table 3 shows the rate at which CO₂ was produced during the fermentation process. As the CO₂ production increased, the amount of citric acid produced also increased generally in all samples but at higher rates in samples inoculated with *A. niger*. The sugar content of the sample were reduced by *A. niger* and *S. cerevisiae*, however *S. cerevisiae* produced a higher rate of sugar utilization (Table 4). *A. niger* showed

slow rate of sugar utilization even in the presence of methanol. Sugar utilization was slightly affected by pH but there appears to be more sugar consumption at pH 5.5 especially in samples inoculated with *S. cerevisiae*.

DISCUSSION

In this study, considerable amount of citric acid were produced from pineapple waste using *A. niger* and *S. cerevisiae* by submerged fermentation. Citric acid, biomass and CO₂ production increased generally in the presence of methanol. It has an enhancing effect on the fungal production of citric acid. Alben and Erkmén (2004) had also reported that the addition of methanol at a concentration of 1 to 4% resulted in a marked increase in the amount of citric acid produced by *A. niger* in spent grain liquor in brewery wastes. In other research it was also reported that the addition of 3 to 4% methanol has not only increased the citric acid production but also increased the pH, biomass, CO₂ production and sugar consumption. All these factors might have caused the gradual increase in temperature from 28°C to 31°C. It has been stated by El-Holi and Al-Delaimy (2003) and Kiel *et al.* (1981) that the inductive effect of methanol for citric acid production may be due to reduction of the inhibitory effect of metal ions. The methanol could also have served as Carbon-source for the microbial cells.

It appears that the citric acid was produced by C-storing cells. The sugar decreased throughout the fermentation period. This indicated that the cells were still viable. There seems to be a link between the storage of carbon and the production of citric acid (Alben *et al.*, 2004). The initial rapid increase in CO₂ production between the sixth and eighth day indicated that the cells were in an exponential phase of growth. The sample inoculated with *A. niger* in the presence of methanol and initial pH of 4.5 produced both the highest citric acid and carbon dioxide concentration. Likewise the sample that produced the least CO₂ concentration (169.80 mg/L) also produced the third to the least citric acid fraction (0.066 % m/v) after the end of the fermentation period. The acidity of the citric acid invariably caused a decrease in pH as citric acid fraction increased.

CONCLUSION

The amount of citric acid produced, sugar consumption, CO₂ production and biomass concentration increased with the addition of methanol. *A. niger* produced the highest amount of citric acid in a medium containing methanol with an initial pH of 4.5. However, *S. cerevisiae* is also a potential candidate for bioconversion of pineapple waste to citric acid.

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